

Affinity patterns in international collaboration: an asymmetrical perspective applied to French–North African co-publications

Paul Khayat*, Tyler Martindale** and David Campbell***

*p.khayat@elsevier.com

ORCID: 0009-0002-1388-7037

Analytical Services, Elsevier, Canada

**t.martindale1@elsevier.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-2589-9089

Analytical Services, Elsevier, Canada

***d.campbell@elsevier.com

ORCID: 0000-0003-3806-3237

Analytical Services, Elsevier, Canada

Abstract

An Asymmetrical Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI_{Asym}) is introduced to capture preferential ties between countries while accounting for the perspective of the leading country in scientific co-publications. Unlike the traditional PAI, it assesses country–country affinities assuming that the country of the corresponding author plays a more significant role in shaping partnerships as opposed to treating all countries as equal contributors. Joint publications led by France with North African partners (Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia), or vice-versa, revealed distinct trends of asymmetrical preferences when analyzed in the context of the global co-publication network since 1996. Early on, both groups had similar and strong affinity for each other regardless of who led the research. Later on, the affinity diverged as France's partnership preference declined when in a leading role, more steeply compared to North African countries' affinity to partner with France when they were leading. The usefulness of PAI_{Asym} is discussed from various perspectives.

1. Introduction

International collaboration in scientific research has experienced significant growth over the past few decades (Aksnes & Sivertsen, 2023). International collaboration enriches research by bringing together diverse perspectives, methodologies, and expertise. Co-publications with international partners often lead to high-quality knowledge and greater scientific impact (Franceschet & Costantini, 2010; Wilsdon, 2011; Guerrero Bote, Olmeda-Gómez & de Moya-Anegón, 2013; Van Raan, 1998;), to increased organizational performance (McGiffin, 2021) and to increased individual productivity (Rostan, Ceravolo & Metcalfe, 2014) and are instrumental in solving complex scientific problems (Sonnenwald, 2007). They are also key in addressing global challenges (e.g., climate change, infectious diseases) that transcend national boundaries (Parker & Kingori, 2016), and allow researchers to have access to funding, data, and facilities not available locally (Lee, Fonseca & Bess, 2023). Monitoring international collaboration practices and patterns helps institutions assess their global engagement and evaluate the effectiveness of science policies promoting such collaboration.

Many different bibliometric indicators have been used to measure international collaboration. Among them, the Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI) is used to identify the preferred partners of a given country in co-publication networks (Zitt, Bassecoulard & Okubo, 2000; Chinchilla-

Rodríguez et al., 2018, 2021). This indicator highlights the strength of relationships between pairs of countries while considering all other associations worldwide and provides a portrait of preferred partnerships in their global context that accounts for various dimensions, such as cultural, linguistic, geographical, and economical proximity (Zitt, Bassecouard & Okubo, 2000; Choi, 2012; Gueye et al., 2022). In addition, it has the benefit of being size-independent, which makes it relevant in detecting strong international ties with small countries.

Despite these nuances of the PAI in revealing relevant collaboration ties, however, this indicator (as well as all other traditional international collaboration indicators) treats all co-publications between country pairs as equal bilateral partnerships, even though some entities may play a more central role in driving the research (McNutt et al., 2018). Dissociating this dimension in bilateral partnerships would bring a deeper understanding of the collaboration practices between two countries. Indeed, identifying patterns of collaborations based on the inherent asymmetry in co-authors' contributions to publications can, for example, reveal how research ecosystems evolve over time (Al-Jamimi, BinMakhashen & Bornmann, 2022), how power dynamics manifest within research teams (González-Alcaide et al., 2017), and help to highlight the role that leadership can play in securing funding, especially for lower-income partners (Rose et al., 2023).

In this study, we introduce a modified version of the PAI which accounts for the asymmetrical dimension of leadership in joint publications. As proxy for determining leadership in research partnerships, we use the corresponding author, who often coordinates research efforts (He et al., 2021; Bordons et al., 2014; Moya-Anegón et al., 2013). This Asymmetrical Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI_{Asym}) relies on the asymmetrical contributions to publications between two countries identified based on the affiliated country of the corresponding author. To present this novel indicator, we focus on the relationship between France and its ancient colonies in North Africa (Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia), with strong cultural, linguistic (partially) and economical proximity. France and these North African countries exhibit a high propensity to partner in scientific research (i.e., high PAI) (Zitt, Bassecouard & Okubo, 2000). With the PAI_{Asym} indicator, we examined whether these strong ties depend on who is leading the research and aim to provide researchers, funding agencies, and policymakers with insights that can help understand the dynamics in scientific collaboration and foster more inclusive and equitable research practices.

2. Methods

In this study, we made use of the Scopus database and included all scientific document types (i.e., mainly journal articles, reviews, conference papers, books, and book chapters) published between 1996 and 2023. Scopus indexes with each publication the affiliation of authors and their authorship role. This allowed us to identify the country of all authors contributing to a publication, including that of the corresponding author which was taken as a proxy for assigning leadership in research work. With these data, we computed the following indicators:

- 1- Number of co-publications: Full counting was used to attribute credit to a country, irrespective of the number of co-authors from a given country. Two approaches were taken to account for co-publications between country pairs: (a) All bilateral co-publications were considered (which served to calculate the PAI), or (b) only co-publications in which a country in a pair was assigned leadership, as determined by the corresponding author's country, were included (which served to calculate the asymmetrical version of the PAI).

In the first approach, if a publication has four addresses with French affiliation, one with Spanish, and one with Moroccan, it is attributed once to each pair France–Spain, France–Morocco, Spain–Morocco, providing a bidirectional measure with equal contribution of each country in a pair. In the asymmetrical approach, if the corresponding author has a Moroccan affiliation, the co-publication will be attributed to the directional link between Morocco–France and Morocco–Spain, but not to France–Spain, France–Morocco, Spain–Morocco, and Spain–France. Each approach resulted in a country–country co-publications matrix (199x199 countries and with the diagonal set to empty values), which fed into the computations of the PAI indicators described below. It is noteworthy that in the asymmetrical approach, publications in which the corresponding author had dual affiliations (i.e., from France and Morocco) were excluded in the pairwise co-publication links to ensure a clear delineation of leadership roles within each bilateral collaboration. In the context of this study, which focuses on the links between France and its North African partners, when either country in a pair was leading the collaboration efforts, dual affiliations resulted in the removal of approximately 14% of co-publications for France–Tunisia, 12% for France–Morocco and 10% for France–Algeria.

- 2- The Probability Affinity Index (PAI): The PAI indicator is computed for each country pair as the actual number of bilateral co-publications (C_{xy}) between countries C_x and C_y , divided by the expected number of bilateral co-publications links (Exp_{xy}):

$$PAI_{xy} = \frac{C_{xy}}{Exp_{xy}}$$

The expected collaboration is defined as:

$$Exp_{xy} = T \times \left(\left(\frac{C_x}{T} \times \frac{C_y}{T-C_x} \right) + \left(\frac{C_y}{T} \times \frac{C_x}{T-C_y} \right) \right)$$

Where C_x and C_y are the total number of co-publications of each of these countries with all other countries worldwide, and T is the sum of all pairwise co-publications of all countries in the network.

- 3- The Asymmetrical Probability Affinity Index (PAI_{Asym}): The PAI_{Asym} indicator is used to identify the preferred partners of a country in pairwise country co-authorship networks while considering the role of leadership in co-publications. Thus, instead of being based on the total number of co-publications between two countries as used for the traditional PAI, the PAI_{Asym} is based on the number of bilateral co-publications between countries C_x and C_y , in which C_x was assigned leadership and C_y was the participant ($C_{xL \rightarrow yP}$), relative to the expected number of bilateral co-publications links ($Exp_{xL \rightarrow yP}$):

$$PAI_{asym} = \frac{C_{xL \rightarrow yP}}{Exp_{xL \rightarrow yP}}$$

The expected collaboration is defined as:

$$Exp_{xL \rightarrow yP} = C_{xL} \times \frac{C_{yP}}{T_P - C_{xP}}$$

Where C_{xL} and C_{xP} are the total number of co-publications of C_x with all other countries, when it is leading (L) or participating (P) in the co-publications. C_{yP} is the total co-publications of C_y with all other countries when C_y is participating, and T_P is the total number of pairwise co-publications of all countries as participants. The PAI is then transformed between -1 and +1 (maximum departure below or above expectation,

representing the least or the most preferred partnerships). Zero values indicate neutral preference.

3. Results

3.1 Collaboration between France and its North African partners irrespective of leadership

We first examined trends in the association between France and its North African partners using the traditional approach of assigning co-publications in a collaboration network (equal bilateral contribution). Since 1996, joint scientific publications between France and its North African partners have increased by more than 5% annually (CAGR of 5.7% with Morocco, 7.8% with Algeria and 9.8% with Tunisia) (Figure 1, left panel). These publications have exhibited more extensive international interaction over the years. In 2009, most co-publications were purely bilateral, only involving France and one North African partner, while in 2023 publications involving France–Algeria or France–Tunisia involved 4 countries on average (including France and a North African partner) and publications involving France–Morocco involved 6 countries on average (Figure 1, right panel).

Figure 1: Research collaboration involving France and its North African partners (1996–2023): Trends in the number of co-publications (left) and average number of countries contributing to these publications (right).

Based on these co-publication patterns, we measured the propensity of each pair of countries to scientifically collaborate with one another, while accounting for the size of each country (in publication volume) and each country’s co-publications with all other countries. This is represented by the traditional PAI.

As shown in Figure 2, the PAI in 1996 was very high between all country pairs ($PAI > 0.97$). The PAI between France–Algeria (blue) and France–Tunisia (green) remained stable for about two decades but has been gradually declining over the past 5–6 years. The collaboration affinity between France and Morocco (orange), however, displayed a different pattern; it sharply declined earlier on (around 2009), followed by a gradual increase a few years later (around 2016) to reach a PAI of 0.82 (about 15% lower than the initial value). Interestingly, the annual decreasing trends in collaboration affinity paralleled the increasing trends in the average number of countries involved in the publications in which France and a North African partner also participated (see Figure 1, right panel). As such, widening international collaboration networks results in a decrease in the PAI patterns.

Figure 2: Annual trends in PAI between France and its North African partners (1996–2023).

3.2 Collaboration between France and its North African partners with respect to leadership

To assess if the collaboration affinity patterns described above were influenced by considering leadership in co-publications, we computed the number of co-publications between each pair of countries when either country was leading the research (based on the corresponding author's country). These co-publications are therefore a subset of those described in the previous section, as they don't include joint publications when neither country was leading (i.e. the corresponding author is from another country).

Figure 3 (left panel) depicts the trends in co-publications between each country pair when France was leading (solid lines) versus when the North African partner was leading (dashed lines). While all co-publications trends increased since 1996, they clearly did so more intensely when co-publications were led by one of the North African countries instead of led by France. This asymmetrical relationship is further quantified by the ratio of France-led co-publications over co-publications not led by France (Figure 3, right panel). Taking the collaboration between France and Morocco as an example, the results show that the number of co-publications gradually shifted from being largely led by France in 1996 (1.86 times more often), to being largely dominated by Morocco's leadership in 2023 (about twice more often).

Figure 3: Leadership in research collaboration involving France and its North African partners (1996–2023): Trends in the number of co-publications led by one or the other country (left), and ratio of France-led co-publications (right).

As for the PAI, we computed the asymmetrical PAI (PAI_{Asym}) which is meant to account for the asymmetrical collaboration relationship between each country pair. The analysis revealed a clear distinction in preferred partnerships depending on which country was leading the research. As shown in Figure 4, when France was taking the leading role in the collaboration efforts (solid lines), its affinity to collaborate with either North African country has gradually decreased over the years. Such decline has been accentuated in the past decade, reaching PAI_{Asym} values 8% lower than in 1996. Conversely, when one or the other North African partner led the collaboration efforts (dashed lines), it maintained a relatively higher affinity to collaborate with France during the study period. These PAI_{Asym} patterns also slightly decreased in time but remain higher than the PAI_{Asym} when France led. Overall, these findings indicate that over the years North African countries have a high preference for collaborations with France, while concurrently taking on a more prominent role in leading research initiatives within these collaborations. On the other hand, France has diverged from its strong collaboration ties with these North African countries when leading research activities.

Figure 4: Annual trends in PAI_{Asym} between France and its North African partners (1996–2023).

3.3 Collaboration affinity between other European countries and North African countries

Are these observed patterns of PAI_{Asym} specific to France’s association with its North African partners or do they also translate to other scientific collaboration links that are not as strongly driven by historical ties? We addressed this potential specificity by analyzing the PAI_{Asym} between each North African country and other, selected EU countries. For each North African country, its EU partner was selected based on the number of joint publications, where each country in a pair had to lead at least 5 co-publications by year. This threshold allowed for a

minimum of stability in the signal. Only Belgium, Spain and Germany exceeded that threshold with each North African country (except for Spain with Tunisia). It is noteworthy that each of these EU countries has unique characteristics that may explain, to a certain extent, the co-publication links with North African countries: Belgium for partially sharing linguistic characteristics (French language), Spain for geographical proximity, and Germany for volume of scientific contributions. These characteristics can indeed favor the probability of engaging in scientific collaborations (Zitt, Bassecoulard & Okubo, 2000; Choi, 2012; Gueye et al., 2022).

Figure 5 illustrates the PAI_{Asym} among the various country pairs. In some cases, when a North African country assumes a leading role in research collaborations the affinity with its EU counterpart tends to be higher compared to scenarios where it does not lead, as indicated by the dashed versus solid lines. In other cases, however, the opposite pattern is observed. These results highlight the distinct nature of these asymmetrical collaboration patterns which fluctuate in time and are dependent on the country–country relationship. Importantly, these patterns are quite distinct from those involving North African countries and France (see Figure 4).

Overall, the present findings underscore the unique dynamics characterizing interactions between each country pair, with the asymmetrical collaboration affinity patterns serving as indicators of shifts in bilateral interactions at certain periods in time. This insight can aid in identifying strengths, gaps and opportunities in bilateral collaboration efforts, thus offering valuable input to inform global engagement policies and international cooperation initiatives.

Figure 5: Annual trends in PAI_{Asym} between selected EU countries and North African partners (1996–2023).

4. Discussion

The present study introduced the asymmetrical Probabilistic Affinity Index (PAI_{Asym}) indicator which provides insights into the dynamics of international research collaborations, particularly in the context of asymmetrical contributions to scientific publications. By analyzing the contributions of corresponding authors to scientific publications, which is taken as a proxy for determining leadership in joint publications (He et al., 2021; Moya-Anegón et al., 2013), the PAI_{Asym} seeks to uncover whether the country–country preference to partner in scientific research changes depending on which country is leading in the collaborative efforts. Using the strong historical associations between France and its former North African colonies as a case study, we found that since 1996 France has been leading fewer joint publications with its North African partners, while the latter have been taking on a more prominent role in leading research papers within these collaborations. This shift in contributions resulted in a decrease in France’s probabilistic affinity to collaborate with these North African countries over time, while at the same time it did not change as much the strong preference of any North African country to partner with France. The results based on the Asymmetrical PAI indicator thus highlight distinct dynamics in collaboration practices that would not have been revealed otherwise using the traditional PAI indicator.

A number of potential factors may explain the distinct patterns in collaboration affinity between France and its North African partners. First, the stronger Asymmetrical PAI when collaborative efforts are driven by the North African country may potentially be attributed to mobility factors (El-Ouahi et al., 2021; Robinson-García et al., 2019). Particularly, North African researchers who studied and worked in France and subsequently returned to their home countries may have maintained collaboration ties with former colleagues and institutions, while acting as principal investigators and corresponding authors in these partnerships. Given that around 10–15% of corresponding authors exhibited dual affiliations, it is likely that these authors predominantly involve North African scholars that initially maintained their linkage to their French institution while adding their new affiliation (Robinson-García et al., 2019). In time, as North African researchers stop being affiliated to their French institutions, they nonetheless maintain a strong and active partnership. Future studies will aim at investigating this dimension.

Second, the question arises as to why France, when it is leading the research, has a lower affinity to preferentially collaborate with North African researchers compared with the other way around. One possible explanation that merits further investigation could be related to the incentive for international collaboration between partners at different scientific and economic development stages, as well as the perceived benefits of those collaborations (Lee, Fonseca & Bess, 2023). On the one hand, Global South and emerging countries, given their smaller capacity in terms of funding and infrastructural resources, may be more driven to maintain and grow their collaborative efforts with developed countries, even when they are taking on a more prominent leadership role in research. In contrast, Global North countries may be less inclined to preferentially collaborate with Global South countries, as their incentive when they are leading the research may be more focused on capacity building and productivity. These differences in collaboration incentives between partners could contribute to the asymmetrical patterns of affinity observed in this study.

The present findings highlight the complex interplay of historical and socio-economic ties, mobility patterns, and collaborative preferences that shape international research dynamics. Future studies could adopt other, more inclusive approaches that consider a broader range of

authorship roles and affiliations. Implementing a multi-dimensional analysis that accounts for distinct contributions within collaborations could provide a more nuanced understanding of leadership dynamics in international research partnerships. Additionally, exploring alternative methodologies or refining existing criteria to balance clarity and inclusivity in determining leading countries could enhance the accuracy and reliability of collaborative assessments. By examining changes in collaboration affinity patterns while considering the drivers in research efforts, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the evolving landscape of research collaborations between countries, informing global engagement and inclusive policies and international cooperation initiatives.

1. Open science practices

The Asymmetrical Probabilistic Affinity Index presented in this study was built using Scopus, a proprietary data source. However, it can be implemented with most large-scale bibliographic databases. As such, the aim of this conference paper is to invite constructive feedback on the approach as well as to share the methodology with the community.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: David Campbell and Paul Khayat

Methodology: David Campbell and Paul Khayat

Data curation: Paul Khayat

Formal Analysis: Paul Khayat

Writing – original draft: Paul Khayat and Tyler Martindale

Writing – review & editing: Paul Khayat, David Campbell and Tyler Martindale

Competing interests

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